

Importance of *Chakrasana* in Present Generation

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Yoga provide us a simple remedies, facile skills and procedure of good health and hygiene to gain physical and mental fitness in less time.^[2] *Yoga* is praised by modern medical science because it increase immunity, give disease free life and decrease the stress of present fast life. It is a scientific procedure by which we can develop our own inner strength with inself. In Sanskrit language *Yoga* means "adduction", add the soul of human from the God. *Yoga* provides us moral and spiritual growth but also useful in prevent physical and mental disease.^[3] *Yoga* and *Asana* effect the physiology of important anatomical structure during procedure and steps.^[4] The definition of *Asana* is "*Sthira Sukham Asanas*"^[5] which means well balanced, pleasant position of body. *Asana* are the "skillful exercises" that gives physical and mental power and tone the body-mind for further exercise.^[6] *Asana* helps to synchronize the mind with body.^[7] We all follow a certain set of medications and exercises to protect our mind as well as the body parts. The situation in getting the medical facilities is very expensive due to globalization. The ancient medicine created by the Siddhas is called siddha medicine and it contains eight types of *Yoga's* as a part of the medication. The word *Asana* means "Seat". It also refers to be at the same place. *Yogasana* helps in protecting the inner organs of the body and to maintain the body as young. The motto of doing the *Asana* is to keep the organs in a certain place and there by controlling the mind. *Asanas* are the primary steps of *Yoga* methods. The physical exercises bring unwanted side effects to the body. But *Yogasana's* gives the strength to the inner and the outer parts of the body and protects the mind as well.^[8]

ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is the science of life. It plays an important role to prevent and treat the disease. *Ayurveda* specifically deals with mind body balance. The main part of it is *Yoga* and *Asana*. *Yoga* provide us a simple remedies, facile skills and procedure of good health. *Asana* gives physical and mental power and tone the body-mind for further exercise. *Chakrasana* is often referred to as the Wheel Pose. It reduces the stress and tension in the body and the eye sight becomes sharp. By doing this *Asana* helps strengthens the back and increases the elasticity of the spine. *Chakrasana* (Wheel Pose) reduces the fat and muscles in abdomen area and tones the digestive and reproductive organs process.

KEYWORDS: *Yoga, Asana, Chakrasana, Wheel Pose, Abdomen area*

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda play an important role to prevent and treat the disease. It is the science of life. Health is disturbed today by the sedentary lifestyle, physical and mental pressure or stress, abnormal personal habits and food habits which cause many disease. According to various texts the primary goal of *Ayurveda* is – "*Swasthasya Swastya Rakshanam, Aturasya Vikara Prashamanam*"^[1] which means increasing the good health and treat the disease. *Ayurveda* specifically deals with mind body balance. The main part of it is *Yoga* and *Asana*. It is essential to being healthy. *Yoga* appeared at the time of the *Vedas* and *Upanishads*. *Yoga* is India's oldest scientific, ideal devotional regulation. It is a process of teaching the brain and growing its capacity of fine perceptions.

Yogasana

Patanjali Yoga described about eight branches –*Yama, Niyama, Asana, Pranayama, Pratyahara, Dharna, Dhyana, Samadhi*. *Patanjali Yoga* given third place to *Asana*^[9], while "*Hatha Yoga*" given first place to "*Asana*" because it giving physical and mental happiness. "Ha" means sun which means energy of solar plexus, "Tha" means moon which means energy of the emotions, present in the limbic system of brain, so both the energy come together in the *Yoga*.^[10] If *Asanas* is done accurately in relaxed and pleasant atmosphere, the muscles of the body get relax because these relaxing impulses go back to the brain and relax it. Other benefits are mental balance, good health, calmness of mind. The ancient *Yogacharyas* advised about the mastery of one *Asana*. *Chakrasana* (Wheel Pose) reduces the fat and muscles in abdomen area and tones the digestive and reproductive organs process.^[11]

Aim and Objectives

- To elaborate the benefits and anatomical structures of *Chakrasana*.
- To escape from injuries which held by doing *Chakrasana*.

Material and Methods

- Texts related to *Yoga-Asana* and their commentaries.
- Other source are online information, print media, journals etc.

Chakrasana-

Chakrasana, also called *Urdva Dhanurasana* is an *Asana*. Sanskrit: ऊर्ध्वधनुरासन; *Urdhva* Upward, *Dhanur* – Bow, *Asana* – Pose; The *Urdhva Dhanurasana* is a backbend and also an *Asana* that forms a part of the trailing off exercises in an *Ashtanga Yoga* regimen. It is also called the *Chakrasana* or the Wheel Pose, apart from being called the Upward Facing Bow Pose. When the pose is assumed, it resembles a wheel or an upward facing bow. This *Asana* is known to give the spine great flexibility. When done as a part of an acrobatic or a gymnastic routine, it is called the back bridge. This *Asana* must be performed only when your stomach and bowels are empty. It is best to have a meal at least four to six hours before your practice so that the food is digested well enough and you are energized for the workout. It is best to practice *Yoga* in the morning. But in the event you cannot manage to take out time in the morning, you can do it in the evening as well.^[12] This has obtained its name because the body will become like a wheel while doing this *Asana*. Therefore, this *Asana* got another name called wheel pose *Asana*. The complete part of this *Asana* is called as “*Poorna Chakrasana*”.^[13]

Name- *Chakrasana* (Wheel Pose)

Level –Advanced

Position- Prone

Type - Inversion, Forward-Bend, Back-Bend, Stretch, Strength

Chakras- Crown *Chakra* (*Sahasrara Chakra*) , Throat *Chakra* (*Vishuddha Chakra*) , Solar Plexus (*Manipura Chakra*)

Doshas (*Ayurveda*)- *Vata* , *Pitta*

Stretches- Abdomen, Thorax, Lung

Strengthens- Back, Legs, Arms, Vertebral column, Abdomen, Buttocks, Wrists^[14]

Procedure of Chakrasana

Below you can find step by step procedure for how to do *Chakrasana* with images.

- Lie down on the *Yoga* mat looking upwardly.
- Fold your legs and keep it down below your butt. Make sure that your sole of the feet touches the floor.

- Bring both of your hands and keep it beneath the shoulders like the fingers see the legs.

- Inhale deep breath and keep your hands and legs on the floor. Then slowly raise your hip, shoulder and the head from the floor.

- Then keep your neck loosely and bend your back as much as possible.
- Stay on the same posture for a minute with normal breath and come back to normal stage by slowly exhaling the breath.
- In the above *Asana*, if the legs and the hands touch each other it is called as *Poorna Chakrasana*.

Benefits of Chakrasana

We can get many benefits of our body parts by doing this *Asana*, especially abdomen areas.

- The chest enhances and the lungs get more oxygen.
- It reduces the stress and tension in the body and the eye sight becomes sharp
- By doing this *Asana* helps strengthens the back and increases the elasticity of the spine.
- It reduces the fat and muscles in abdomen area and tones the digestive and reproductive organs process.
- It strengthens the muscles of hands and the legs.
- It induces the endocrine glands and maintains the metabolism normally.
- It induces the brain cells and refreshes the brain.
- It rectifies the uterine and menstrual problems in women.
- It stimulates the process of the liver, spleen and kidneys.
- It purifies the blood and gives good peace and clarity of thoughts and removes the unwanted tiredness and the afraid.
- It cures the hernia and the kidney become stimulated and refreshed.^[15]

Precautions and Contraindications

These are some points of caution you must keep in mind before doing this *Asana*.

1. It is best to avoid this *Asana* if you have tendonitis in the wrists or carpal tunnel syndrome.
2. If your lower back starts to hurt due to the extension, immediately come out of the pose.
3. You must steer clear of this *Asana* if you have a shoulder impingement.
4. Do not do this *Asana* if you suffer from headaches or high blood pressure.

Beginner's Tips

As a beginner, when you do this pose, you will find your feet and knees splaying as you lift your body to assume this pose. This will tend to compress your lower back. So, you can use a strap on your thighs to keep them hip-width apart throughout the *Asana*. If you need to keep your feet in place, use a block between them such that the sides of the big toes press the edges of the block.^[16]

Anatomy

- *Chakrasana* flow benefits the following muscles -
- Arms and Shoulders
- Biceps and Triceps
- Core (Abs)
- Neck^[17]

Advanced Pose Alterations

To intensify the pose, you can do the *Eka Pada Urdhva Dhanurasana*. For this, once you get into the Wheel Pose, move your weight on one foot. Then, as you exhale, bend the other foot at the knee, and pull it into your torso. Exhale and stretch it out upwards. Hold the pose for a few seconds, and then bring your knee to the floor as you exhale. Repeat using the other leg.

The Science Behind The *Chakrasana* (*Urdhva Dhanurasana*)

Like most other *Yoga Asanas*, this one also works on our mind, body, and emotions. This *Asana* encapsulates the whole essence of back bending and moves you towards joy and fearlessness. It is known to enhance the vital force that surrounds your heart and the distributive force that is all over your body (*prana* and *vyana*), therefore helping you become more aware of things and also building the courage

to battle any challenge that comes your way. This *Asana* focuses on flexing the frontal part of the body that includes the shoulders, the intercostal muscles, the wrists, the hip flexors, and the quadriceps. It also imparts strength to the shoulders, sacrum, wrists, and arms, and makes them more stable. If done correctly, it also helps to rotate the thighs and arms and also engage the hamstrings.^[18]

Chakrasana flow Breath Awareness

The most challenging part of *Chakrasana* Flow (Wheel Pose Flow) is using the neck, shoulders, hands, core and head efficiently so as to not cause any heaviness or stiffness while in *Vinyasa*. These muscles and parts of the body are instead supported by the breathing process to make everything move smoothly. While all *Yoga* poses, no doubt demand the awareness of the body and breathing, in this practice of the *Chakrasana* Flow (Wheel Pose Flow), the emphasis is placed even more on breathing to ensure a safe and smooth movement. Given below are the step-by-step instructions to follow the breathing process for *Chakrasana* Flow:

1. **Inhale:** From *Shavasana* (Corpse Pose) place the hands at the shoulders and inhale to take the legs behind your head in the variation of *Halasana* (Plough Pose).
2. **Exhale:** Lift the shoulders and the neck pressing the palms on the floor as you exhale to come to *Phalakasana* (Plank Pose).
3. **Inhale:** Raise the chest and shoulders as you inhale to come to *Urdhva Mukha Shvanasana* (Upward Facing Dog Pose).
4. **Exhale:** Move the hips up as you exhale to come to *Adho Mukha Shvanasana* (Downward Facing Dog Pose).

Note: The movement from supine to prone is done in one breath. For better effect and smooth flow of the neck and shoulders, holding the chin in *Jalandhara Bandha* (Chin Lock) is advised. It is important to take care while practicing the *Chakra* Flow (Wheel Flow) and for the same, the support of a *Yoga* teacher's guidance is encouraged and advised.^[19]

Preparatory Poses

- Bhujangasana*
- Setu Bandha Sarvangasana*
- Urdhva Mukha Shvanasana*
- Virasana*

Follow-Up Poses

- Ardha Matsyendrasana*
- Supta Padangusthasana*

This *Asana*, even though deemed a basic one, is extremely challenging. But if done correctly and regularly, it can not only make you stronger, but also more compassionate, fearless, and happy.^[20]

Conclusion

Yoga is the science of life. *Yoga* is India's oldest scientific, ideal devotional regulation. It is a process of teaching the brain and growing its capacity of fine perceptions. *Yoga* provide us a simple remedies, facile skills and procedure of good health and hygiene to gain physical and mental fitness in less time. Daily practice of *Yoga*, *Asana* and *Pranayama* with proper attention gives result pure blood supply to body parts like heart, liver, lungs, pancreas, intestine, kidney, ligaments, tissues, muscles, and glands of human body. It also increases the digestion power. It control power of the

sense organs and awareness. *Yoga* and *Asana* will give disease and stress free healthy life. Anatomical structures during breath and postures as lungs, ligaments, muscles and bones, ligaments, joints, muscles and tendon during movement are involved. Anatomical structures and their work are behind the scientific benefit of *Yoga* and *Asana*. Wheel pose stimulates the process of the liver, spleen and kidneys. *Chakrasana* (Wheel Pose) purifies the blood and gives good peace and clarity of thoughts and removes the unwanted tiredness and the afraid.

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